

SPECIFIC ASPECTS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE SPIRITUAL AND CULTURAL SPHERE IN THE NEW UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: Acceleration of socio-economic processes in New Uzbekistan development is not only optimal for solving global problems of humanity search for ways, but also to preserve material and spiritual values and to the next generation the development of issues such as transmission, the study of the essence of national and religious values are extensively analyzed in the article

Key words: national value, religion, development, nation, society, spirituality, future

In a historically short period of time, under the direct leadership of the head of our state, the Strategy of Actions on the five priority directions of the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan - a long-term strategy for the sustainable development of society and the state - was developed, which marks the beginning of a completely new stage of fundamental and rapid democratic reforms.

First, the Strategy of Actions served as a foundation stone for the construction of New Uzbekistan. The need to develop a new policy for New Uzbekistan and a long-term strategy for the country's development based on the understanding that only countries that keep pace with the times and implement the necessary reforms for the modernization of society and the state can be competitive in today's rapidly developing world. was recorded.

As the head of our state noted, "In this strategy, we defined the rights and freedoms and legal interests of every citizen living in our country as the highest value. It should be noted that the New Development Strategy of Uzbekistan begins a new stage of national development. From now on, we will organize our activities based on the new principle of "man - society - state" [1].

Secondly, the state of New Uzbekistan belongs to the people. The main goal of the reforms implemented in the country is to protect a person, his life, freedom, honor, dignity, legal needs and interests. The activities of the Virtual reception of the President of Uzbekistan and People's receptions make a great contribution to ensuring the personal, political, economic, social and cultural rights and freedoms of a person.

At the initiative of our President, the National Strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Human Rights was adopted and started to be implemented.

Ensuring the rights and freedoms of citizens and implementing international human rights standards in national legislation and law enforcement practice has become the main criterion of democratic reforms aimed at creating comfortable and decent living conditions for the people [2].

We know that in Uzbekistan, which aims to build a democratic society, from the first days of independence, it is the basis of our state's policy to carry out economic and political reforms together with spiritual reforms and spiritual revival and spiritual renewal in accordance with the spirit of the times. it has been.

"When thinking about the philosophical roots of the national-spiritual and moral foundations of building a democratic society, it is assumed that it is based on the conclusions of the science of philosophy, which is the father of all sciences. An example of this is that each of the European nations, which began to restore their national statehood in the Renaissance and the Middle Ages, created their own spirituality. These values were formed on the basis of the national philosophies that emerged on the basis of the specific values and mentality of the peoples who had their own statehood after the collapse of the Roman Empire. Therefore, the Italian, English, and French philosophy of that time served to unite the society to which he belonged. At the same time, the philosophical doctrines and educational views created at the base of these national schools made a great contribution to the treasury of human culture.

There are theories, teachings and ideologies that have had a great impact on the development of societies and civilizations. Creative ideas of Zoroaster, Socrates, Plato, Confucius, Alisher Navoi, Mahatma Gandhi and others have left an indelible mark in history. Entrepreneur Amir Temur's creative ideas and activities made a great contribution to the rapid development of Eastern culture. The same can be said about German philosophy, which became famous with the names of thinkers such as Kant, Hegel, and Nissche. In particular, Hegel's philosophy, which has real national characteristics, rose to the level of the state ideology of the Prussian monarchy, which broke away from the Austrian Empire and followed the path of independence"[3].

The secular roots of national spirituality consist of a set of political, economic, and cultural relations characteristic of the enlightened world. Over the centuries, humanity has gradually moved towards secularism. Universally recognized principles and features such as the rule of law, political pluralism, interethnic harmony, and interreligious tolerance form the basis of a secular society. Human rights and freedoms, including freedom of conscience, are guaranteed by law.

The ideology of such a society develops on the basis of the concept that "Secularism is not secularism", that is, it does not deny the role and importance of religion in the life of society.

The religious roots of national spirituality mean that it is inextricably linked with the human mind and spirit, and therefore its ideological roots go back to religious teachings. "In other words, in many ideologies, we see that the noble ideas mentioned in divine books such as "Psalms", "Torah", "Bible" and "Quran" have been expressed to a certain extent.

The teachings of Confucius and Lao Si, who founded the development path of the Chinese people, were also based on religious views. These teachings have been the national ideology of the country for centuries" [4].

In the period of strengthening independence, it is necessary to solve a number of problems and tasks related to the fundamental historical turn in the political, economic, cultural, spiritual life of the society in all aspects. Such a huge task and responsibility requires our people to fully understand the process of spiritual renewal on the one hand, and on the other hand to rely on it in building a democratic society. After all, it is becoming a factor of national-spiritual renewal, growth and development.

"Development rises to a higher level in the conditions where secular and religious ideas enrich each other. A vivid example of this is the times when great intellectuals such as Imam Bukhari and Musa Khorazmi, Imam Motrudi and Abu Rayhan Beruni, Imam Fazzali and Ibn Sina, Imam Termizi and Abu Nasr Farabi lived and worked.

The dialectic of the struggle between goodness and evil, creativity and destruction has determined the historical forms and essence of national spirituality since time immemorial. That is, contrary to the ideologies of invasion, getting rich at the expense of others, aggression, and fanaticism, the ideas of freedom, independence and justice have continuously emerged and become the victorious flag of the peoples" [5].

In the analysis of the issue of moral renewal, the Concept of the First President of Uzbekistan I. A. Karimov "Deepening democratic reforms and development of civil society in our country" has not lost its importance. It shows the following principles of spiritual development:

- loyalty to universal values;
- strengthening and developing the spiritual heritage of the people;
- free realization of human potential;
- patriotism [6].

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Side panel The development strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2022-2026, which was adopted at the initiative of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev, and the adoption of many decrees and decisions aimed at reforming society, is the program of the renewal process in our country. and reforms are being implemented on its basis.

The issue of modernization of the society was analyzed as the main issue of the agenda in the pre-election meetings of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. At the meetings, the task was set to achieve radical development, modernization and active participation of the population in the processes of modernization of all sectors of our country, to improve the living standards of people not only in the city, but also in remote rural areas. Shavkat Mirziyoyev spoke about the need to modernize industries, agriculture, technology, science, culture, and spirituality in Uzbekistan on an innovative basis at meetings with representatives of the voters of each region [7].

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